

PSTeCEQL: A NOVEL EVENT QUERY LANGUAGE FOR VANET'S UNCERTAIN EVENT STREAMS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the complex event processing technology has been used to process the VANET's temporal and spatial event streams. However, we usually cannot get the accurate data because the device sensing accuracy limitations of the system. We only can get the uncertain data from the complex and limited environment of the VANET. Because the VANET's event streams are consist of the uncertain data, so they are also uncertain. How effective to express and process these uncertain event streams has become the core issue for the VANET system. To solve this problem, we propose a novel complex event query language PSTeCEQL (probabilistic spatio-temporal constraint event query language). Firstly, we give the definition of the possible world model of VANET's uncertain event streams. Secondly, we propose an event query language PSTeCEQL and give the syntax and the operational semantics of the language. Finally, we illustrate the validity of the PSTeCEQL by an example.

KEYWORDS

VANET, Internet of vehicles, Event stream, Event-driven Architecture, uncertain data, event query language, Mobile systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the VANET and Internet of Vehicles have made great achievements [1]. The VANET is a typical mobile system and Internet of Things' system. In VANET system, there are a lot of sensing devices in the vehicles and these sensing devices will produce a large number of temporal and spatial event streams when they are moving quickly.

Many scholars have processed the VANET's data steams by the complex event processing technology. Moody K has proposed a complex event query language SpaTec and this language can describe the spatial and temporal properties of the event streams of VANET [2,3]. Jin B has presented a event query language CPSL and this language can describe the relationship between the various temporal and spatial properties of the events [4]. Yixiang Chen has proposed a complex event query language STeCEQL and the language can describe the spatial and temporal relationships of the event streams in VANET [5,6].

The conventional data processing systems often assume that the data is accurate. However, with the rapid development of the sensor networks and the Internet of Things, the uncertain data of these systems causes the relevant researchers. According to statistics, the probability of the RFID tags, which can be correctly recognized by the sensors, is about 60% to 70%. The uncertain data in the sensor networks and the Internet of Things are ubiquitous and cannot be ignored. These uncertain data were produced by the following main reasons: 1) the original data is not accurate. The data collection devices' accuracy is limited, such as: various types of sensors, RFID scanning equipment, GPS equipment. In addition, the sensing device has different data precision in

different working conditions. 2) In the data transmission process, the accuracy of the data was affected by the transmission bandwidth, transmission protocol and the other conditions.

Since the existing complex event processing language cannot effectively express the uncertain event in VANET. This paper presents a novel complex event processing language to VANET: PSTeCEQL (probabilistic spatio-temporal constraint event query language). The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: section 2 introduces the related works. Section 3 describes the possible world model of VANET'S uncertain event stream. Section 4 presents the syntax of PSTeCEQL. Section 5 gives operational semantics of PSTeCEQL. The last Section concludes this paper.

2. RELATED WORKS

In the event-driven architecture systems, data is abstracted as the event and the uncertain data is abstracted as the uncertain data. In the studies of the uncertain events, there are two types uncertain event model: Probability theory model [7-9] and the fuzzy set theory model [10-12]. Our uncertain event model: the possible world model which based on the probability theory, is very widely recognized now [13,14].

For the uncertain data processing problem, the current research results focus on the uncertain database fields. Many scholars have conducted in-depth research in the uncertain database's storage, indexing and query. Since the data streams arrive at very fast rate and are very large amount, the data stream processing system cannot directly use the methods and techniques of the conventional database processing system. Compared with the uncertain database's research, the studies of uncertain data stream processing system is still in its infancy. Cormode has proposed the uncertain data stream query system with probability parameters [15]. Zhang has designed the frequently query on uncertain data stream query method [16]. As an important uncertain data processing area, the uncertain event stream processing system has made these major achievements: Kanagal has extended the relational database system in order to be able to deal with uncertain event streams [17]. Christopher has proposed an uncertain event stream processing system which named Lahar [18].

In the VANET system, users usually only need query the events with specially trustworthiness. In view of this situation, we have proposed a novel uncertain VANET's event stream query language: PSTeCEQL (probabilistic spatio-temporal constraint event query language). Comparing with the other researches, ours mainly have the following improvements: the PSTeCEQL language can reduce the numbers of the uncertain event instances by setting the probability threshold manner, so to improve the efficiency of the event stream processing system.

3. POSSIBLE WORLD MODEL OF VANET'S UNCERTAIN EVENT STREAMS

In order to deal with the VANET's uncertain data, we should firstly establish the model of these uncertain data. The possible world model is the most common uncertain data model, which evolved many instances from the model and these instances called the possible world data instances. The types of the possible world model are: the relational data model, semi-structured data model and data flow models, etc.

The data flow's possible world model is as below:

Definition 1: Suppose each tuple can get more value in a discrete domain D , the trustworthiness of the data stream for each tuple is based on a probability density function of these discrete

domains. For example, a tuple is described as $\langle I_1:P_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle I_m:P_m \rangle$, then $\forall s \in [1, m]$, there is $I_s \in D$, $\Pr[I_s]=P_s$, and $\sum_1^m P_s \leq 1$, and said the probability density function data value P_s is the trustworthiness.

For example, a speed sensor has generated a data stream and the speed range is $(0, 80]$, the possible data flow are: $\{ \langle 25:0.7 \rangle, \langle 28:0.2 \rangle \}, \langle 26:0.85 \rangle, \langle 35:0.6 \rangle, \langle 40:0.13 \rangle, \dots \}$.

In the VANET system, we use this type uncertain data flow's possible world model. Because the VANET's uncertain data is a multi-source data, so we extended the above model to the VANET's possible world model as bellow:

Suppose a tuple can be represented $[\langle I_{11}:P_{11} \rangle, \dots, \langle I_{1m}:P_{1m} \rangle], \dots, \langle I_{n1}:P_{n1} \rangle, \dots, \langle I_{nm}:P_{nm} \rangle]$, then $\forall s \in [1, m]$, there is $I_s \in B$, $\Pr[I_s]=P_s$, and $\sum_1^m P_s \leq 1$.

Figure1. The uncertain data flow of VANET

Example 1: As shown in Figure 1, assume that there are three type data of the data stream of the VANET: the time data, the position data and the speed data. We denoted these data as T, L, V: T represents a time data value, L represents a spatial data value and V represents a velocity value.

In the event-driven architecture, a set of meaningful data were looked as a based event instance.

Therefore, in the event-driven architecture VANET system, the uncertain data have caused the event is also uncertain. Based on the above possible world model of the uncertain data of VANET system, we give the definition of the possible world model of the event stream of VANET.

The uncertain based event stream is shown as Figure 2, and the definition is as below:

Definition 2: A based event tuple is described as $\langle E_1:P_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle E_m:P_m \rangle$, then $\forall s \in [1, m]$, there is $\Pr[I_s]=P_s$, and $\sum_1^m P_s \leq 1$, and said the probability density function data value P_s is the trustworthiness.

Figure2. The uncertain based event flow of VANET

According to this definition, the fourth data of the Example 1's data stream: $[(\langle T_{41}:0.3 \rangle, \langle T_{42}:0.2 \rangle, \langle T_{43}:0.4 \rangle), (\langle L_{41}:0.1 \rangle, \langle L_{42}:0.54 \rangle, \langle L_{43}:0.23 \rangle), (\langle V_{41}:0.35 \rangle, \langle V_{42}:0.6 \rangle)]$ represents a uncertain based event instance:

$\langle E_1: P_1 \rangle, \langle E_2: P_2 \rangle, \langle E_3: P_3 \rangle, \langle E_4: P_4 \rangle, \langle E_5: P_5 \rangle, \langle E_6: P_6 \rangle, \langle E_7: P_7 \rangle, \langle E_8: P_8 \rangle,$
 $\langle E_9: P_9 \rangle, \langle E_{10}: P_{10} \rangle, \langle E_{11}: P_{11} \rangle, \langle E_{12}: P_{12} \rangle, \langle E_{13}: P_{13} \rangle, \langle E_{14}: P_{14} \rangle, \langle E_{15}: P_{15} \rangle,$
 $\langle E_{16}: P_{16} \rangle, \langle E_{17}: P_{17} \rangle, \langle E_{18}: P_{18} \rangle).$

Among them, $E_1 = (T_{41}, L_{41}, V_{41}), E_2 = (T_{42}, L_{41}, V_{41}), E_3 = (T_{43}, L_{41}, V_{41}), E_4 = (T_{41}, L_{42}, V_{41}), E_5 = (T_{42}, L_{42}, V_{41}), E_6 = (T_{43}, L_{42}, V_{41}), E_7 = (T_{41}, L_{43}, V_{41}), E_8 = (T_{42}, L_{43}, V_{41}),$
 $E_9 = (T_{43}, L_{43}, V_{41}), E_{10} = (T_{41}, L_{41}, V_{42}), E_{11} = (T_{42}, L_{41}, V_{42}), E_{12} = (T_{43}, L_{41}, V_{42}),$
 $E_{13} = (T_{41}, L_{42}, V_{42}), E_{14} = (T_{42}, L_{42}, V_{42}), E_{15} = (T_{43}, L_{42}, V_{42}), E_{16} = (T_{41}, L_{43}, V_{42}), E_{17} = (T_{42}, L_{43}, V_{42}), E_{18} = (T_{43}, L_{43}, V_{42}).$

There are $3 \times 3 \times 2 = 18$ based event instances in the possible world model of the event and the trustworthiness of each instance can be calculated according to the probability theory's formula $\Pr[E] = \Pr[T] \times \Pr[L] \times \Pr[V]$. For example: $P_1 = 0.3 \times 0.1 \times 0.35 = 0.0105$.

The complex event instance can be calculated by the based event instances; therefore, we can define the uncertain complex event possible world model by the based event possible world model.

Definition 3: A complex event tuple is described as $\langle \langle CE_1:P_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle CE_m:P_m \rangle \rangle$, then $\forall s \in [1, m]$, there is $\Pr[CE_s]=P_s$, and $\sum_1^m P_s \leq 1$, and said the probability density function data value P_s is the trustworthiness.

Example 2: $CE_1 = (E_1 \vee E_2) \wedge E_3$

Which, E_1 's possible events: $\langle E_{11}:0.35 \rangle, \langle E_{12}:0.42 \rangle, \langle E_{13}:0.13 \rangle$,

E_2 's possible events: $\langle E_{21}:0.26 \rangle, \langle E_{22}:0.58 \rangle$,

E_3 's possible events: $\langle E_{31}:0.35 \rangle, \langle E_{32}:0.42 \rangle, \langle E_{33}:0.13 \rangle$,

And the CE_1 possible events are:

$\langle \langle (E_{11} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{31} \rangle : P_1 \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{12} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{31} \rangle : P_2 \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{13} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{31} \rangle : P_3 \rangle,$
 $\langle \langle (E_{11} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{31} \rangle : P_4 \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{12} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{31} \rangle : P_5 \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{13} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{31} \rangle : P_6 \rangle,$
 $\langle \langle (E_{11} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{32} \rangle : P_7 \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{12} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{32} \rangle : P_8 \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{13} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{32} \rangle : P_9 \rangle,$
 $\langle \langle (E_{11} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{32} \rangle : P_{10} \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{12} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{32} \rangle : P_{11} \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{13} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{32} \rangle : P_{12} \rangle,$
 $\langle \langle (E_{11} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{33} \rangle : P_{13} \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{12} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{33} \rangle : P_{14} \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{13} \vee E_{21}) \wedge E_{33} \rangle : P_{15} \rangle,$
 $\langle \langle (E_{11} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{33} \rangle : P_{16} \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{12} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{33} \rangle : P_{17} \rangle, \langle \langle (E_{13} \vee E_{22}) \wedge E_{33} \rangle : P_{18} \rangle,$
 ...)

As shown in the possible world model of the based event instance and the complex event instance, the numbers of the event instance will increase quickly with the event's complex level increasing and the computing system will be difficult to accomplish the processing task. How to efficient processing the huge collection of instances of the possible world is the main difference between the normal event processing system and the uncertain event processing system.

However, in the practical application of VANET's, not all events are useful to the user's making decision. Users usually will limit the trustworthiness of the event during the querying. For example: an user requires the trustworthiness of a based event instance is greater than 0.5, another user requires the trustworthiness of a complex event instance is greater than 0.3, etc.

According the above ideas, we proposed a novel event query language: PSTeCEQL.

4. SYNTAX OF PSTeCEQL

It is assumed that the syntax structure of the constants and the variables are known. For example: the variable is a collection of the non-null letters. So, the syntax of the PSTeCEQL is as follows:

1. The uncertain object identifier expressions **POBEXP**:

$$pob \exp ::= TRUE : P | FALSE : P | x_{id} = ID : P | x_{id} \neq ID : P$$

$$| pobexp_1 \wedge pobexp_2 : P | pobexp_1 \vee pobexp_2 : P$$

2. The general uncertain numerical attribute expressions **PABEXP**:

$$pab \exp ::= TRUE : P | FALSE : P | x_a = A : P | x_a \neq A : P$$

$$| x_a > A : P | x_a \geq A : P | x_a < A : P | x_a \leq A : P$$

$$|pabexp_1 \wedge pabexp_2 : P|pabexp_1 \vee pabexp_2 : P$$

3. The uncertain temporal attribute expressions **PTBEXP**:

$$ptbexp ::= TRUE : P|FALSE : P|x_t BEFORE T : P|x_t EQUAL T : P$$

$$|x_t OVERLAP T : P|x_t DURING T : P$$

$$|ptbexp_1 \wedge ptbexp_2 : P|ptbexp_1 \vee ptbexp_2 : P$$

4. The uncertain spatial attribute expressions **PLBEXP**:

$$plbexp ::= TRUE : P|FALSE : P|x_{loc} EQ LOC : P|x_{loc} OP LOC : P$$

$$|x_{loc} IN LOC : P|x_{loc} NORTH LOC : P|x_{loc} EAST LOC : P$$

$$|x_{loc} NORTHEAST LOC : P|x_{loc} NORTHWEST LOC : P$$

$$|plbexp_1 \wedge plbexp_2 : P|plbexp_1 \vee plbexp_2 : P$$

5. The uncertain event expressions **PEBEXP**:

$$pebexp ::= TRUE : P|FALSE : P|pobexp; ptbexp; plbexp; pabexp : P$$

$$|pebexp_1 \wedge pebexp_2 : P|pebexp_1 \vee pebexp_2 : P$$

$$|pebexp_1 BEFORE pebexp_2 : P|pebexp_1 EQUAL pebexp_2 : P$$

$$|pebexp_1 OVERLAP pebexp_2 : P|pebexp_1 DURING pebexp_2 : P$$

$$|pebexp_1 EQ pebexp_2 : P|pebexp_1 OP pebexp_2 : P|pebexp_1 IN pebexp_2 : P$$

$$|pebexp_1 NORTH pebexp_2 : P|pebexp_1 EAST pebexp_2 : P$$

$$|pebexp_1 NORTHEAST pebexp_2 : P|pebexp_1 NORTHWEST pebexp_2 : P$$

For example: $e_1=((CarId=10584:0.89); (CarTime DURING (19:18:20, 19:19:10):0.93); (CarLoc NORTH \{(1052,306), (1052,307), (1052,308)\}:0.94); ((V<100):0.96);(Acceleration <30):0.94):0.6);$

$e_2=((LightId=63254:0.95); (LightTime DURING (19:18:20, 19:18:40):0.93); (Signal=GREEN:0.99)):0.87);$

$e_3=(e_1 \wedge e_2:0.5);$

The syntax of the PSTeCEQL language listed above and the following are the operational semantics of the language.

5. OPERATIONAL SEMANTIC OF PSTeCEQL

Each expression's value was decided by the current environmental of the variable storage. In VANET system, the subscribers have received event instances and stored the event instance in the memory firstly. Then the event instances will be processed by the system following the principle of first-come, first-served (FCFS). Finally, the PSTeCEQL expressions' value will be calculated.

Based on the above setting, the operational semantics of the PSTeCEQL as below:

1. The operational semantics of the **POBEXP**:

$$(1) \frac{\langle x_{pid}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (TRUE:P), \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{id} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P),$$

$$(2) \frac{\langle x_{pid}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (FALSE:P), \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{id}[\emptyset/x_{id}, 0/x_{pid}] \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 < P),$$

$$(3) \frac{\frac{\langle x_{pid}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{id}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow ID_0}}{\langle (x_{id}=ID:P), \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{id} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (ID_0 = ID),$$

$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pid}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{id}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow ID_0}}{\langle (x_{id}=ID:P), \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{id}[\emptyset/x_{id}, 0/x_{pid}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, ID_0 \neq ID),$$

$$(4) \frac{\frac{\langle x_{id}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{id}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow ID_0}}{\langle (x_{id}=ID:P), \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{id} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (ID_0 \neq ID),$$

$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{id}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{id}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow ID_0}}{\langle (x_{id}=ID:P), \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{id}[\emptyset/x_{id}, 0/x_{pid}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, ID_0 = ID),$$

$$(5) \frac{\frac{\langle x_{pid1}, \delta_{id1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pid2}, \delta_{id2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (obexp1:P'), \delta_{id1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1), \delta_{id1} \rangle \text{ and } \langle (obexp2:P''), \delta_{id2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_2), \delta_{id2} \rangle}}{\langle (obexp1 \wedge obexp2:P), (\delta_{id1}, \delta_{id2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{id1}, \delta_{id2}) \rangle},$$

if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $P_1 \times P_2 \geq P$,

$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pid1}, \delta_{id1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pid2}, \delta_{id2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (obexp1:P'), \delta_{id1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_{id1}[\emptyset/x_{id1}, 0/x_{pid1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle (obexp2:P''), \delta_{id2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_{id2}[\emptyset/x_{id2}, 0/x_{pid2}] \rangle}}{\langle (obexp1 \wedge obexp2:P), (\delta_{id1}, \delta_{id2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{id1}[\emptyset/x_{id1}, 0/x_{pid1}], \delta_{id2}[\emptyset/x_{id2}, 0/x_{pid2}]) \rangle},$$

if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 < P$;

$$(6) \frac{\frac{\langle x_{pid1}, \delta_{id1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pid2}, \delta_{id2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (obexp1:P'), \delta_{id1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1), \delta_{id1} \rangle \text{ or } \langle (obexp2:P''), \delta_{id2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_2), \delta_{id2} \rangle}}{\langle (obexp1 \vee obexp2:P), (\delta_{id1}, \delta_{id2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{id1}, \delta_{id2}) \rangle},$$

if $(P_1 \geq P'$ or $P_2 \geq P'')$ and $(P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P$;

$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pid1}, \delta_{id1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pid2}, \delta_{id2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (obexp1:P'), \delta_{id1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_{id1}[\emptyset/x_{id1}, 0/x_{pid1}] \rangle \text{ and } \langle (obexp2:P''), \delta_{id2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_{id2}[\emptyset/x_{id2}, 0/x_{pid2}] \rangle}}{\langle (obexp1 \wedge obexp2:P), (\delta_{id1}, \delta_{id2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{id1}[\emptyset/x_{id1}, 0/x_{pid1}], \delta_{id2}[\emptyset/x_{id2}, 0/x_{pid2}]) \rangle},$$

if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $(P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P$;

2. The operational semantics of the **PABEXP**

$$(1) \frac{\langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (TRUE:P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_a \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P),$$

$$(2) \frac{\langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (FALSE:P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_a[\emptyset/x_a, 0/x_{pa}] \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 < P),$$

$$(3) \frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a=A:P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_a \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (A_0 = A),$$

$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a=A:P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_a[\emptyset/x_a, 0/x_{pa}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, A_0 \neq A),$$

- (4) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a := A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_0), \delta_a \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (A_0 \neq A),$
- $\frac{\frac{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a := A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_0), \delta_a [\emptyset / x_a, 0 / x_{pa}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, A_0 = A),$
- (5) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a > A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_0), \delta_a \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (A_0 > A),$
- $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a > A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_0), \delta_a [\emptyset / x_a, 0 / x_{pa}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, A_0 \leq A),$
- (6) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a \geq A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_0), \delta_a \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (A_0 \geq A),$
- $\frac{\frac{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a \geq A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_0), \delta_a [\emptyset / x_a, 0 / x_{pa}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, A_0 < A),$
- (7) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a < A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_0), \delta_a \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (A_0 < A),$
- $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a < A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_0), \delta_a [\emptyset / x_a, 0 / x_{pa}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, A_0 \geq A),$
- (8) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a \geq A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_0), \delta_a \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (A_0 \geq A),$
- $\frac{\frac{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_a, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow A_0}}{\langle (x_a \geq A : P), \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_0), \delta_a [\emptyset / x_a, 0 / x_{pa}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, A_0 < A),$
- (9) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa1}, \delta_{a1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pa2}, \delta_{a2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (abexp_1 : P'), \delta_{a1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_1), \delta_{a1} \rangle \text{ and } \langle (abexp_2 : P''), \delta_{a2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_2), \delta_{a2} \rangle}}{\langle (pabexp_1 \wedge pabexp_2 : P), (\delta_{a1}, \delta_{a2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{a1}, \delta_{a2}) \rangle},$
- $\text{if } P_1 \geq P' \text{ and } P_2 \geq P'' \text{ and } P_1 \times P_2 \geq P;$
- $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa1}, \delta_{a1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pa2}, \delta_{a2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (abexp_1 : P'), \delta_{a1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_1), \delta_{a1} [\emptyset / x_{a1}, 0 / x_{pa1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle (abexp_2 : P''), \delta_{a2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_2), \delta_{a2} [\emptyset / x_{a2}, 0 / x_{pa2}] \rangle}}{\langle (pabexp_1 \wedge pabexp_2 : P), (\delta_{id1}, \delta_{id2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{id1} [\emptyset / x_{id1}, 0 / x_{pid1}], \delta_{id2} [\emptyset / x_{id2}, 0 / x_{pid2}]) \rangle},$
- $\text{if } P_1 < P' \text{ or } P_2 < P'' \text{ or } P_1 \times P_2 < P;$
- (10) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa1}, \delta_{a1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pa2}, \delta_{a2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (abexp_1 : P'), \delta_{a1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_1), \delta_{a1} \rangle \text{ or } \langle (abexp_2 : P''), \delta_{a2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_2), \delta_{a2} \rangle}}{\langle (pabexp_1 \vee pabexp_2 : P), (\delta_{a1}, \delta_{a2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{a1}, \delta_{a2}) \rangle},$
- $\text{if } (P_1 \geq P' \text{ or } P_2 \geq P'') \text{ and } (P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P;$
- $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pa1}, \delta_{a1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pa2}, \delta_{a2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (abexp_1 : P'), \delta_{a1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_1), \delta_{a1} [\emptyset / x_{a1}, 0 / x_{pa1}] \rangle \text{ and } \langle (abexp_2 : P''), \delta_{a2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_2), \delta_{a2} [\emptyset / x_{a2}, 0 / x_{pa2}] \rangle}}{\langle (pabexp_1 \vee pabexp_2 : P), (\delta_{a1}, \delta_{a2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE : P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P), (\delta_{a1} [\emptyset / x_{a1}, 0 / x_{pa1}], \delta_{a2} [\emptyset / x_{a2}, 0 / x_{pa2}]) \rangle},$
- $\text{if } P_1 \geq P' \text{ and } P_2 \geq P'' \text{ and } (P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P;$

3. The operational semantics of the PTBEXP

- (1) $\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (TRUE : P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE : P_0), \delta_t \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P),$

- (2)
$$\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (FALSE:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_t[\emptyset/x_t, 0/x_{pt}] \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 < P);$$
- (3)
$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_t, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow T_0}}{\langle (x_t \text{ BEFORE } T:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_t \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (T_0 \text{ BEFORE } T);$$

$$\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (x_t \text{ BEFORE } T:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_t[\emptyset/x_t, 0/x_{pt}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, T_0 \overline{\text{BEFORE}} T);$$
- (4)
$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_t, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow T_0}}{\langle (x_t \text{ EQUAL } T:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_t \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (T_0 \text{ EQUAL } T);$$

$$\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (x_t \text{ EQUAL } T:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_t[\emptyset/x_t, 0/x_{pt}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, T_0 \overline{\text{EQUAL}} T);$$
- (5)
$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_t, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow T_0}}{\langle (x_t \text{ OVERLAP } T:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_t \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (T_0 \text{ OVERLAP } T);$$

$$\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (x_t \text{ OVERLAP } T:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_t[\emptyset/x_t, 0/x_{pt}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, T_0 \overline{\text{OVERLAP}} T);$$
- (6)
$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_t, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow T_0}}{\langle (x_t \text{ DURING } T:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_t \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (T_0 \text{ DURING } T);$$

$$\frac{\langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (x_t \text{ DURING } T:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_t[\emptyset/x_t, 0/x_{pt}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, T_0 \overline{\text{DURING}} T);$$
- (7)
$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pt1}, \delta_{t1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pt2}, \delta_{t2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (tbexp_1:P'), \delta_{t1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1), \delta_{t1} \rangle \text{ and } \langle (tbexp_2:P''), \delta_{t2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_2), \delta_{t2} \rangle}}{\langle (ptbexp_1 \wedge ptbexp_2:P), (\delta_{t1}, \delta_{t2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{t1}, \delta_{t2}) \rangle}},$$

$$\text{ if } P_1 \geq P' \text{ and } P_2 \geq P'' \text{ and } P_1 \times P_2 \geq P;$$

$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pt1}, \delta_{t1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pt2}, \delta_{t2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (tbexp_1:P'), \delta_{t1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_{t1}[\emptyset/x_{t1}, 0/x_{pt1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle (tbexp_2:P''), \delta_{t2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_{t2}[\emptyset/x_{t2}, 0/x_{pt2}] \rangle}}{\langle (ptbexp_1 \wedge ptbexp_2:P), (\delta_{t1}, \delta_{t2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{t1}[\emptyset/x_{t1}, 0/x_{pt1}], \delta_{t2}[\emptyset/x_{t2}, 0/x_{pt2}]) \rangle}},$$

$$\text{ if } P_1 < P' \text{ or } P_2 < P'' \text{ or } P_1 \times P_2 < P;$$
- (8)
$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pt1}, \delta_{t1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pt2}, \delta_{t2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (tbexp_1:P'), \delta_{t1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1), \delta_{t1} \rangle \text{ or } \langle (tbexp_2:P''), \delta_{t2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_2), \delta_{t2} \rangle}}{\langle (ptbexp_1 \vee ptbexp_2:P), (\delta_{t1}, \delta_{t2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{t1}, \delta_{t2}) \rangle}},$$

$$\text{ if } (P_1 \geq P' \text{ or } P_2 \geq P'') \text{ and } (P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P;$$

$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pt1}, \delta_{t1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pt2}, \delta_{t2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (tbexp_1:P'), \delta_{t1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_{t1}[\emptyset/x_{t1}, 0/x_{pt1}] \rangle \text{ and } \langle (tbexp_2:P''), \delta_{t2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_{t2}[\emptyset/x_{t2}, 0/x_{pt2}] \rangle}}{\langle (ptbexp_1 \vee ptbexp_2:P), (\delta_{t1}, \delta_{t2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{t1}[\emptyset/x_{t1}, 0/x_{pt1}], \delta_{t2}[\emptyset/x_{t2}, 0/x_{pt2}]) \rangle}},$$

$$\text{ if } P_1 \geq P' \text{ and } P_2 \geq P'' \text{ and } (P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P;$$

4. The operational semantics of the PLBEXP:

- (1)
$$\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (TRUE:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{loc} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P);$$
- (2)
$$\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (FALSE:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 < P);$$
- (3)
$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ EQ } LOC:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{loc} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (LOC_0 \text{ EQ } LOC);$$

$$\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ EQ } LOC:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, LOC_0 \overline{\text{EQ}} LOC);$$
- (4)
$$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ OP } LOC:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{loc} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (LOC_0 \text{ OP } LOC);$$

- $$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ OP } LOC:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, LOC_0 \overline{OP} LOC),$$
- (5) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ IN } LOC:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{loc} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (LOC_0 \text{ IN } LOC),$
- $$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ IN } LOC:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle}, \text{ if } P_0 < P \text{ or } (P_0 \geq P, LOC_0 \overline{IN} LOC),$$
- (6) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ NORTH } LOC:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{loc} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (LOC_0 \text{ NORTH } LOC),$
- $$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ NORTH } LOC:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle},$$
- if $P_0 < P$ or $(P_0 \geq P, LOC_0 \overline{NORTH} LOC),$
- (7) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ EAST } LOC:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{loc} \rangle}, \text{ if } (P_0 \geq P) \text{ and } (LOC_0 \text{ EAST } LOC),$
- $$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ EAST } LOC:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle},$$
- if $P_0 < P$ or $(P_0 \geq P, LOC_0 \overline{EAST} LOC),$
- (8) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ NORTHEAST } LOC:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{loc} \rangle},$
- if $(P_0 \geq P)$ and $(LOC_0 \text{ NORTHEAST } LOC),$
- $$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ NORTHEAST } LOC:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle},$$
- if $P_0 < P$ or $(P_0 \geq P, LOC_0 \overline{NORTHEAST} LOC),$
- (9) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ NORTHWEST } LOC:P), \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_0), \delta_{loc} \rangle},$
- if $(P_0 \geq P)$ and $(LOC_0 \text{ NORTHWEST } LOC),$
- $$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle x_{loc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow LOC_0}}{\langle (x_{loc} \text{ NORTHWEST } LOC:P), \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_0), \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle},$$
- if $P_0 < P$ or $(P_0 \geq P, LOC_0 \overline{NORTHWEST} LOC),$
- (10) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc1}, \delta_{loc1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{ploc2}, \delta_{loc2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (l\text{bexp}_1:P'), \delta_{loc1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1), \delta_{loc1} \rangle \text{ and } \langle (l\text{bexp}_2:P''), \delta_{loc2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_2), \delta_{loc2} \rangle}}{\langle (pl\text{bexp}_1 \wedge pl\text{bexp}_2:P), (\delta_{loc1}, \delta_{loc2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{loc1}, \delta_{loc2}) \rangle},$
- if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $P_1 \times P_2 \geq P,$
- $$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc1}, \delta_{loc1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{ploc2}, \delta_{loc2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (l\text{bexp}_1:P'), \delta_{loc1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_{loc1}[\emptyset/x_{loc1}, 0/x_{ploc1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle (l\text{bexp}_2:P''), \delta_{loc2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_{loc2}[\emptyset/x_{loc2}, 0/x_{ploc2}] \rangle}}{\langle (pl\text{bexp}_1 \wedge pl\text{bexp}_2:P), (\delta_{loc1}, \delta_{loc2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{loc1}[\emptyset/x_{loc1}, 0/x_{ploc1}], \delta_{loc2}[\emptyset/x_{loc2}, 0/x_{ploc2}]) \rangle},$$
- if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 < P,$
- (11) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc1}, \delta_{loc1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{ploc2}, \delta_{loc2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (l\text{bexp}_1:P'), \delta_{loc1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1), \delta_{loc1} \rangle \text{ or } \langle (l\text{bexp}_2:P''), \delta_{loc2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_2), \delta_{loc2} \rangle}}{\langle (pl\text{bexp}_1 \vee pl\text{bexp}_2:P), (\delta_{loc1}, \delta_{loc2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{loc1}, \delta_{loc2}) \rangle},$
- if $(P_1 \geq P' \text{ or } P_2 \geq P'')$ and $(P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P,$
- $$\frac{\frac{\langle x_{ploc1}, \delta_{loc1} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{ploc2}, \delta_{loc2} \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (l\text{bexp}_1:P'), \delta_{loc1} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_{loc1}[\emptyset/x_{loc1}, 0/x_{ploc1}] \rangle \text{ and } \langle (l\text{bexp}_2:P''), \delta_{loc2} \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_{loc2}[\emptyset/x_{loc2}, 0/x_{ploc2}] \rangle}}{\langle (pl\text{bexp}_1 \vee pl\text{bexp}_2:P), (\delta_{loc1}, \delta_{loc2}) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_{loc1}[\emptyset/x_{loc1}, 0/x_{ploc1}], \delta_{loc2}[\emptyset/x_{loc2}, 0/x_{ploc2}]) \rangle},$$

if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $(P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P$;

5. The operational semantics of the **PEBEXP**:

- (1) $\frac{\langle x, \delta \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle \langle TRU E : P \rangle, \delta \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_0 \rangle, \delta \rangle}$, if $(P_0 \geq P)$;
- (2) $\frac{\langle x, \delta \rangle \rightarrow P_0}{\langle \langle FALSE : P \rangle, \delta \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_0 \rangle, \delta[\emptyset/x, 0/x_p] \rangle}$, if $(P_0 < P)$;
- (3) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pid}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_2 \text{ and } \langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_3 \text{ and } \langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_4}{\langle \langle obexp : P' \rangle, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \rangle, \delta_{id} \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle tbexp : P'' \rangle, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_2 \rangle, \delta_t \rangle$
 $\langle \langle lbexp : P''' \rangle, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_3 \rangle, \delta_{loc} \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle abexp : P'''' \rangle, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_4 \rangle, \delta_a \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle pobjexp : P \rangle, \delta \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \times P_2 \times P_3 \times P_4 \rangle, \delta \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $P_3 \geq P'''$ and $P_4 \geq P''''$ and $P_1 \times P_2 \times P_3 \times P_4 \geq P$;
- (4) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{pid}, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{pt}, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow P_2 \text{ and } \langle x_{ploc}, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow P_3 \text{ and } \langle x_{pa}, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow P_4}{\langle \langle obexp : P' \rangle, \delta_{id} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \rangle, \delta_{id}[\emptyset/x_{id}, 0/x_{pid}] \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle tbexp : P'' \rangle, \delta_t \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_2 \rangle, \delta_t[\emptyset/x_t, 0/x_{pt}] \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle lbexp : P''' \rangle, \delta_{loc} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_3 \rangle, \delta_{loc}[\emptyset/x_{loc}, 0/x_{ploc}] \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle abexp : P'''' \rangle, \delta_a \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_4 \rangle, \delta_a[\emptyset/x_a, 0/x_{pa}] \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle pobjexp : P \rangle, \delta \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \times P_2 \times P_3 \times P_4 \rangle, \delta[\emptyset/x, 0/x_p] \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_3 < P'''$ or $P_4 < P''''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 \times P_3 \times P_4 < P$;
- (4) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle lbexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle ebexp_1 \wedge ebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3[E_1 \otimes E_2/x, P_1 \times P_2/x_p]) \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $P_1 \times P_2 \geq P$;
- (5) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle \langle ebexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}] \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle pebexp_1 \wedge pebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}], \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}]) \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 < P$;
- (5) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \text{ or } \langle \langle ebexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle pebexp_1 \vee pebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3[E_1 \otimes E_2/x, P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2/x_p]) \rangle}$,
 if $(P_1 \geq P'$ or $P_2 \geq P'')$ and $(P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P$;
- (6) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}] \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle ebexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}] \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle pebexp_1 \vee pebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}], \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}]) \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $(P_1 + P_2 - P_1 \times P_2) \geq P$;
- (6) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle lbexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle ebexp_1 \text{ BEFORE } ebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3[E_1 \otimes E_2/x, P_1 \times P_2/x_p]) \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $P_1 \times P_2 \geq P$ and $(T_1 \text{ BEFORE } T_2)$;
- (7) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle \langle ebexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}] \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle pebexp_1 \text{ BEFORE } pebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}], \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}]) \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 < P$ or $(T_1 \text{ BEFORE } T_2)$;
- (7) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle lbexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle ebexp_1 \text{ EQUAL } ebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3[E_1 \otimes E_2/x, P_1 \times P_2/x_p]) \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $P_1 \times P_2 \geq P$ and $(T_1 \text{ EQUAL } T_2)$;
- (8) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle \langle ebexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}] \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle pebexp_1 \text{ EQUAL } pebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle FALSE : P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}], \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}]) \rangle}$,
 if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 < P$ or $(T_1 \text{ EQUAL } T_2)$;
- (8) $\frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle \langle ebexp_1 : P' \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \rangle, \delta_1 \rangle \text{ and } \langle \langle lbexp_2 : P'' \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_2 \rangle, \delta_2 \rangle}$
 $\langle \langle ebexp_1 \text{ OVERLAP } ebexp_2 : P \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle \langle TRU E : P_1 \times P_2 \rangle, (\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3[E_1 \otimes E_2/x, P_1 \times P_2/x_p]) \rangle}$,

$$\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\frac{\langle (ebexp_1:P'), \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle (ebexp_2:P''), \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}] \rangle}{\langle (pebexp_1 \text{ EAST } pebexp_2:P), (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}], \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}]) \rangle}},$$

if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 < P$ or $(LOC_1 \text{ EAST } LOC_2)$;

$$(15) \frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (ebexp_1:P'), \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1), \delta_1 \rangle \text{ and } \langle (ebexp_2:P''), \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_2), \delta_2 \rangle}}{\langle (ebexp_1 \text{ NORTHEAST } ebexp_2:P), (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3[E_1 \otimes E_2/x, P_1 \times P_2/x_p]) \rangle}},$$

if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $P_1 \times P_2 \geq P$ and $(LOC_1 \text{ NORTHEAST } LOC_2)$;

$$\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\frac{\langle (ebexp_1:P'), \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle (ebexp_2:P''), \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}] \rangle}{\langle (pebexp_1 \text{ NORTHEAST } pebexp_2:P), (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}], \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}]) \rangle}},$$

if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 < P$ or $(LOC_1 \text{ NORTHEAST } LOC_2)$;

$$(16) \frac{\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\langle (ebexp_1:P'), \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1), \delta_1 \rangle \text{ and } \langle (ebexp_2:P''), \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_2), \delta_2 \rangle}}{\langle (ebexp_1 \text{ NORTHWEST } ebexp_2:P), (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (TRUE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3[E_1 \otimes E_2/x, P_1 \times P_2/x_p]) \rangle}},$$

if $P_1 \geq P'$ and $P_2 \geq P''$ and $P_1 \times P_2 \geq P$ and $(LOC_1 \text{ NORTHWEST } LOC_2)$;

$$\frac{\langle x_{p1}, \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow P_1 \text{ and } \langle x_{p2}, \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow P_2}{\frac{\langle (ebexp_1:P'), \delta_1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1), \delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}] \rangle \text{ or } \langle (ebexp_2:P''), \delta_2 \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_2), \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}] \rangle}{\langle (pebexp_1 \text{ NORTHWEST } pebexp_2:P), (\delta_1, \delta_2) \rangle \rightarrow \langle (FALSE:P_1 \times P_2), (\delta_1[\emptyset/x_1, 0/x_{p1}], \delta_2[\emptyset/x_2, 0/x_{p2}]) \rangle}},$$

if $P_1 < P'$ or $P_2 < P''$ or $P_1 \times P_2 < P$ or $(LOC_1 \text{ NORTHWEST } LOC_2)$;

6. CONCLUSIONS

Focusing on VANET's uncertain event stream's processing problem, we have proposed a novel event query language PSTeCEQL in this paper. In this event query language, we have used possible world models to model the uncertain event instances of VANET and called the event's probability is its trustworthiness. Based on the VANET's event model, we have proposed the event query language PSTeCEQL. Then we give the syntax and operational semantics of PSTeCEQL. Finally, we illustrate the validity of the PSTeCEQL by an example.

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